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Introduction

This document is the result of a research activity performed in the framework of the COSME project FoodPackLab2, addressing India and South Africa market in the agrifood sector. One important activity of the project was the organization of meetings: the starting date of the project was 01/09/2020. We thus had to study and to re-design the modality of face-to-face meetings, in particular b2b meetings, in order to cope with pandemic spread, social distancing, travelling restrictions.

The document refers in particular to the European environment and focuses on Italian situations.

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THE NEW COMMUNICATION ERA

1 THE WIDESPREAD DISSEMINATION OF DIGITAL COMMUNICATION

In recent decades, digital technologies have evolved to become key channels for interpersonal communication and interaction to sustain relationships, for the exchange of emotional support, and for the exchange and sharing of work material in jobs, where collaboration and exchange of ideas in content creation are required (Ranie & Wellman, 2012).

This evolution peaked as a result of the restrictions imposed by the lockdown during the pandemic period. Indeed, governments and public health institutions around the world established guidelines for social distancing to combat the COVID - 19 pandemic¹. Although specific restrictions varied between countries, government policies to manage the coronavirus outbreak uniformly imposed the closure of schools, physical shops, non-essential activities, the restriction of transport and public spaces, and social gatherings (Anderson et al., 2020; Chinazzi et al., 2019; Horton, 2020). Under these circumstances, we have witnessed a drastic decrease in public interaction. As opportunities to meet in person changed, new challenges emerged for staying socially connected: during the pandemic first months, industry reports showed that digital media use increased dramatically (Kemp, 2020). Such increases were particularly widespread for social media and messaging apps, but particularly notable was the unprecedented spread of video conferencing apps and programs.

2 THE OBJECTIVES OF THE RESEARCH

As part of the research project, we sought to understand the motivations behind such a pervasive diffusion of digital technologies, outlining the trend in the spread of digital communication among different social classes and assessing its implications. During the research period, we also tried to understand the evolutionary trend of the digital infrastructures adoption, both in people's daily lives and in their working environments, outlining what the guidelines might be for identifying the innovation aspects necessary to ensure a sustainable prosecution of the digital change. This change had its greatest acceleration thanks to the restrictions imposed by governments in order to cope with the Covid 19 pandemic.

3 THE NEED TO STAY CONNECTED AND THE TECHNOLOGY SOCIAL SUPPORT

The Covid 19 pandemic poses a threat not only to physical health, but to people's mental health due to social isolation (Holmes et al., 2020). Using a scientific perspective on mental health will help us better understand the behavior of the population during the pandemic (Holmes, 2014).

Many of the expected consequences of quarantine and social and physical removal measures are themselves key risk factors for mental health problems (Brooks, 2020). These include suicide and self-harm, alcohol and substance abuse, gambling, domestic abuse, and psychosocial risks (such as social disconnection, meaninglessness or anomie, entrapment, cyberbullying, feeling of being a burden, financial stress, bereavement, loss, unemployment, homelessness, and the breakdown of relationships). (O' Connor 2014; Turecki et al., 2019).

¹ World Health Organization. (2020). Coronavirus disease (COVID-19) advice for the public. <https://www.who.int/emergencies/diseases/novel-coronavirus-2019/advice-for-public>

One of the main negative consequences of the COVID-19 pandemic has been the increase in social isolation and loneliness (The Academy of Medical Sciences, 2020), which are strongly associated with anxiety, depression, self-harm, and suicide attempts over a lifetime (Elovainio, 2017; Matthews, 2019).

Reducing feelings of loneliness and promoting feelings of belonging are candidate mechanisms to protect against suicide, self-harm, and emotional problems (O' Connor 2018; Stack 1988).

Social isolation and loneliness are distinct and might represent different risk pathways but according to the evolutionary theory of loneliness (Cacioppo et al., 2006), people suffer distress when separated from their social ties. This aspect, within the COVID-19 containment measures, helps us to better understand the behavior of the population, as it reveals the intrinsic motivation to restore vital connections, especially from a psychological point of view. In light of this, the study found that people are more likely to comply with physical distancing measures only if they feel socially connected, gathering the strength and willpower to adhere to the measures imposed by the government to cope with the pandemic. Further studies (Zacher & Rudolph, 2020) confirmed a widespread concern that distancing measures hurt individuals psychological well-being.

For example, it was found that during the period of the most severe contact restrictions in Germany (March-May 2020), individuals' positive emotions and satisfaction with life decreased. Similarly, compared to pre-pandemic times, mental health decreased in the UK (Smith et al.,2020) and individuals reported relatively high levels of loneliness (Groarke et al.,2020).

Given the unique circumstances of COVID-19, data collection is critical to determine the causal mechanisms associated with poor mental health, including loneliness and feelings of entrapment (Holmes, 2018; Kazdin, 2007).

Social isolation, which during the pandemic and especially during the lockdown period, was experienced by a large part of the population, can be defined as an absence of social contact and personal relationships resulting from the low frequency of social contact with friends, relatives, and neighbours; absence of a discussion network with whom to communicate personal and important issues; and absence of social support, i.e. people to whom one can ask for help in case of need (Eckhard, 2018). Social isolation is determined by a combination of objective and subjective components, including the number of interpersonal contacts, the sense of belonging, and the quality of the social network (Nicholson; 2009).

Objective social isolation represents the tangible aspect of physical separation or absence of interaction with other people, as measured by the frequency of interactions and the size of one's social network. Subjective social isolation is defined as an individual's perception of the quality of relationships with members of their network and includes the constructs of loneliness, perceived social support, and subjective closeness with friends and family (Taylor et al; 2018). Social isolation and lack of social support are correlated with higher rates of depression, whereas having the support of a spouse, friends, and a good neighbourhood is linked to fewer depressive symptoms (Herbolsheimer, 2018).

Loneliness is negatively associated with subjects' emotional well-being and is a risk factor for depressive symptoms (Nilsen et al, 2018); while larger social networks and emotional support received and provided are protective against depressive symptoms (Harasemiw et al, 2018).

Understanding why it is difficult for human beings to refrain from meeting their close contacts, considering theories on loneliness and furthering studies on the fundamental need for belonging in human beings is crucial to understand the reasons behind such a pervasive spread of digital technologies. Still following the evolutionary theory of loneliness proposed by Cacioppo, we can state that individuals perceive social pain

when they are separated from people with whom they feel connected. In turn, this social pain leads to a negative internal state, characterized by feelings of loss of control, anxiety, depression, and lowered self-esteem.

Consequently, people are motivated to repair social disconnections to overcome this state of aversion and achieve feelings of social reward by relying on digital infrastructures.

In this regard, the theory of electronic proximity (Korzenny, 1978) suggests that feelings of (psychological) closeness can also be achieved by employing electronic communication devices. Drawing on psychological theories such as the theory (Sommer, 1967) of small group ecology, it can be argued that perceived psychological distance is not necessarily related to physical distance, but rather that perceived closeness is influenced by the attributes of the communication channel (i.e. the electronic device).

New technologies can offer social support to individuals who are isolated in their homes, the use of them can improve social support, loneliness, social networking, and related factors such as depression, stress, self-esteem, and quality of life (Morris et al; 2014). Online activity can be used to escape the difficulties of real life (Ryan, Chester, Reece & Xenos, 2014), therefore, it seems reasonable to suggest that individuals with depressive symptoms are more likely to use Internet to alleviate symptomatology and suppress the need to remain interconnected.

The literature shows a significant relationship between the perception of subjective social isolation and psychological well-being; especially the increase in depressive symptomatology (Nicholas & Nicholson, 2012). Feeling supported in social relationships acts as a protective factor against depressive symptomatology (Santini et al; 2015), while a sense of loneliness is a risk factor (Nilsen et al, 2018).

The need to belong (Baumeister & Leary, 1995) implies that humans have an evolutionary-based need to form and maintain strong, stable interpersonal relationships and to have frequent, non-adversarial interactions. Based on a synthesis of empirical findings, the authors specified that both strong relationships and frequent contact are important: if interaction occurs with strangers or partners who change, or if people have stable relationships without frequent contact, this is perceived as unsatisfactory. Chronic deprivation is related to negative affect, to the extent that general distress is a consequence of separation from important and stable ties, thus describing a strong connection between stable social relationships and general social support, improving individuals' subjective well-being (Lee et al., 2008).

Similarly, other studies (Lee & Robbins 1995) have introduced the concept of social connectedness to describe a specific aspect of belonging. Social connectedness does not simply describe the network dimension of individuals but is defined "as the subjective awareness of being in close relationship with the social world" (Lee & Robbins, 1998). Although this aspect of belonging mainly refers to lasting relationships (Lee et al., 2001), it has been shown that people feel less socially connected at times when they do not interact with others in any way (Sun et al., 2019).

Thus, research is indicative of how general social support correlates with better health and subjective well-being (e.g. Wang et al., 2003; Zeidner et al., 2016). The close connection between social support and loneliness was also demonstrated in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic-related blockade, e.g., in the UK, with findings that perceived general social support mitigated feelings of loneliness (Groarke et al., 2020).

It is important to note that although social support is often treated as a one-dimensional construct, it must be conceptualized as a multidimensional construct. With this in mind, (House, 1981) defines social support

as the social exchange, an interpersonal transaction involving four different dimensions (emotional concern, instrumental help, information, and evaluation) identifying social relationships as protective factors from stress.

Through this research work, we have tried to understand the reasons for such a widespread diffusion of communication technologies by ascertaining how digital infrastructures are valuable opportunities to compensate for the absence of physical social contact. However, people have various communication channels at their disposal, which can function very differently.

Following the theory of electronic proximity (Korzenny, 1978), the interaction of the characteristics of the channel, the communication objectives, and the characteristics of the individuals determine the experienced proximity to the communication partner. Proximity is conceptualized as the experienced sensation of electronic proximity or presence independent of the actual physical proximity of the communication partners. Although Korzenny's theory focused on group communication in organizations of the time (e.g., audio-conferencing), other authors (Walther & Bazarova 2008) have argued that the theory can also be applied to modern computer-mediated communication.

In line with the assumptions of electronic proximity, technologies can serve to foster social support and social connection when physical contact is not possible. For example, mobile phone contact has been identified as an important facilitator of people's social relationships (Wei & Lo, 2006). Mobile phones seem to facilitate people's symbolic closeness. Especially for geographically isolated people, phone calls with strong ties are an important source of social support to reduce loneliness (Liu et al., 2014).

As found in previous studies (e.g. Lee et al., 2008; Wang et al., 2003; Zeidner et al., 2016), social support and social connectedness are expected to improve the general well-being of the population. However, well-being is a broad concept that can be operationalized in various ways and is influenced by a multitude of processes that tend to be constantly interrelated (Matthews et al. 2009). Commonly, life satisfaction, associated with a balanced emotional state, is considered a fundamental dimension of subjective well-being (e.g. Jose et al., 2012; Lee et al., 2008), recalling that contemporary psychology suggests that happiness is not simply the absence of stress and discomfort. Rather, happiness reflects positive individual traits, bonds with others, and effective life adjustment qualities (Compton and Hoffman 2012). Delving deeper into the aspect of psychological well-being, we can state that social support may even be more important than coping style and life satisfaction in achieving happiness (Chu et al. 2010; Taylor 2011). Hence, the importance of studying well-being in a social context (Helliwell and Putnam 2004; Lakey and Cohen 2000). Further studies (Diener et al., 2010) have also introduced psychological well-being as a central dimension of subjective well-being, addressing the human need for relationships and self-acceptance.

The aforementioned studies show how digital technologies played a decisive and central role in helping people cope with the pandemic, fostering the social well-being that was essential for each individual to respect the limitations imposed to cope with the Covid 19 pandemic. The greatest challenge this pandemic has brought us to face has been a challenge on two levels, the physical level, and the psychological level, and in this the digital infrastructures have played a key role, accompanying us day after day towards the end of the state of the global crisis that has affected every part of our lives.

4 INEQUALITIES IN THE ADOPTION OF DIGITAL INFRASTRUCTURE

In one of the few empirical studies on the pandemic, an attempt was made to understand how communication spread across different social groups by examining the digital communication habits of people from different social backgrounds during physical distancing (van Deursen, 2020).

It has already been shown how digital experiences and habits changed during the period of widespread physical distancing, (e.g., Anderson & Vogels, 2020; GlobalWebIndex, 2020, pp. 10-14; Ipsos, 2020) revealing how people's use of video chats, instant messaging, social media and other methods increased during the early months of the pandemic to compensate for the lack of in-person interactions.

As documented by other works (Beaunoyer et al., 2020), it was found that those able to adopt online alternatives and supplements to typically offline activities (such as work, school, health care, and communication with family and friends) were less affected by both psychologically and occupationally during a public crisis involving physical distancing.

Research on digital inequality has shown that Internet access is not evenly distributed among the general population (Scheerder, 2017) and appropriation theory (Van Dijk Jagm, 2005) explains differences or inequalities in Internet access by considering individuals' personal and positional categories and resources. Internet access itself is considered an appropriation process involving attitudinal access, access to materials, access to skills, and, in the final stage, access to use. The latter involves differences in the type of activities people perform on the Internet. The consequences of the process are the results of Internet use. These results in turn reinforce personal and positional inequalities and unequal distribution of resources. To study the differences in Internet uses and outcomes during the COVID-19 pandemic, it is necessary to understand the types of uses and outcomes at play. Typically, uses and outcomes are studied following conceptual classifications that distinguish different domains, such as economic, social, cultural, or personal domains.

Research on digital inequality suggests that the vast amount of web-based information and communication possibilities around the COVID-19 pandemic is likely to be difficult for sections of the general population to understand and conceptualize. Some frequently observed personal categorical inequalities are gender, age, personality, and health.

Despite the widespread use of digital technologies, it has been seen that not everyone has been equally prepared or willing to increase digital communication (Robinson et al., 2020). It has been ascertained how the adoption of digital infrastructures in such a pronounced manner has exacerbated the digital divide, disproportionately impacting vulnerable groups (Pew Research Center, 2019), who lacked the know-how to effectively use digital media (Hargittai & Micheli, 2019). A major concern of scholars has been directed precisely at the digital exclusion of elderly populations during the pandemic (e.g. Robinson et al., 2020).

Another type of personal inequality considered in this study is traditional literacy, which is known to have a substantial impact on Internet use. Considering the crucial role the Internet is playing in the COVID-19 crisis, a low level of literacy is a potentially major inhibitor of information understanding and engagement in web-based communication (Coiro, 2003; van Deursen 2014 et al., 2014).

Research has long shown that education is one of the most important positional variables in digital divide research, and less digitally literate people face challenges in adopting new methods of digital communication (Hargittai & Micheli, 2019; Hsieh, 2012; Yu et al., 2017), which can be further exacerbated when adoption needs to occur at a rapid pace such as during a pandemic. Supporting these predictions, an empirical study

found that more privileged users, in terms of Internet access and skills, were more likely to inform themselves and communicate with others about the COVID-19 pandemic (van Deursen, 2020).

A possible reason why some people reduced their digital communication during the pandemic, instead of using it as frequently as before, could be the loss of digital support of people and places of free Internet access due to the blocking measures. Family and peers constitute the main sources of digital support (Eynon & Geniets, 2016; Hunsaker et al., 2019; Micheli et al., 2019), which is important for Internet adoption and continued use (Hsieh et al., 2010).

Research on digital inequality theorizes additional interconnected factors that shape who benefits most from the spread of digital technologies.

People are differently disposed to benefit from digital technologies, based not only on who has the skills to use digital technologies, but also on who has quality, reliable and autonomous Internet access (DiMaggio et al., 2004). In this regard, additional challenges in the adoption of digital infrastructures were faced, which included unstable Internet connections and difficulties in maintaining the functionality of devices (Gonzales, 2016; Marler, 2019).

Sociodemographics can predict changes in digital communication based on different abilities to maintain Internet access during a pandemic (Gonzales, 2016). In this regard, we can argue how inequalities become more pronounced in low-income segments of the population, just as they are more relevant for those living in rural areas

When studying differences in Internet uses and outcomes the resources that people can access are often derived from Pierre Bourdieu's theory of capital, which emphasizes the importance of including not only economic but also social and cultural resources in determining one's status and position in society. In the pandemic of COVID-19, economic and social resources are likely important, as previous research has shown that people with greater economic resources, mostly made as income in digital inequality research, are known to use the Internet more effectively and productively (Bourdieu, 1986; DiMaggio 2004). People with more social resources are more likely to have greater access to the Internet.

Thus, it is possible to state that digital inequalities are influenced by a multitude of factors whereby groups are created that have to struggle to keep up with the increased use of digital communication, maintain social or work relationships, and also have psycho-emotional support.

One way to mitigate the growing inequalities during a public health crisis could be to foster closer access to technology by enhancing access to Internet skills, improving attitudinal access, and supporting access to digital infrastructure (van Deursen AJ, van Dijk JA., 2019; Beaunoyer et al., 2020; Seifert et al., 2020).

Digital inequality could thus join other axes of inequality to burden already disadvantaged groups.

Several groups of people have been identified as vulnerable, such as the elderly, the less educated, and people with physical health problems, low levels of literacy, or low levels of Internet skills. In general, people who are already relatively advantaged are more likely to use the information and communication opportunities provided by the Internet to their advantage in a health pandemic, while less advantaged people are less likely to take advantage of them. Therefore, the COVID-19 crisis is also reinforcing existing inequalities (Nguyen, 2020; Nguyen et al., 2020).

The COVID-19 pandemic offers a unique case for studying digital communication behavior, and for fully understanding people's changing uses of digital media during a period of widespread physical distancing as digital inequality is a major concern among national and international scholars and policymakers.

5 DIGITAL INFRASTRUCTURE AND VIRTUAL MOBILITY

COVID-19 has triggered a strong momentum in online activities in different parts of the world, but despite the growth in the use of the Internet to carry out online activities, many people around the world have not had the opportunity to replace in-person activities with online activities due to the nature of their profession or lack of equipment, resources and infrastructure (e.g. lack of or poor Internet connection, lack of personal computers or smartphones).

Although there is a minority of the population has not had easy access to digital infrastructure, online activities have had an impact on the lives of the population. The adoption of online activities during COVID-19 offered the opportunity to carry out certain aspects of daily life without the need to physically travel. (Beck, Hensher and Wei, 2020; de Haas, Faber and Hamersma, 2020; Shamshiripour, Rahimi, Shabanpour and Mohammadian, 2020). In this context, we cannot avoid talking about so-called "virtual mobility". Virtual mobility is generically understood as: "A range of activities based on the use of information and communication technologies (including e-learning) that realize or foster international and collaborative experiences in a work context, a training context, or a learning context". This phenomenon affected traditional urban mobility during COVID-19 and impacts are expected in the post-pandemic period as well.

Online activities and virtual mobility can reshape urban mobility as they are linked to changes in travel behavior, transport systems and land uses (Andreev, Salomon, & Pliskin, 2010; Battarra, Gargiulo, Tremitterra, & Zucaro, 2018; Ettema, 2018; Gössling, 2018; Kwan, Dijst, & Schwanen, 2007; Levinson & Krizek, 2017; Line, Jain, & Lyons, 2011; Mokhtarian, Salomon & Handy, 2006; Mouratidis et al., 2021; Ozbilen, Wang, & Akar, 2021; van Wee, 2015; van Wee, Geurs, & Coro, 2013).

Online activities replace some travel by allowing people to participate in activities remotely but can generate other types of travel due to the time and money saved by this substitution. Conducting remote activities can also have long-term implications for land use. Residential and work locations can adapt to remote online activities such as teleworking and online shopping. People or workplaces may, for example, move to more remote locations. Physical workplaces may disappear. These changes, in turn, may also lead to changes in travel behavior. The wider adoption of online activities that occurred during COVID-19 is likely to play an important role in long-term mobility (Conway et al., 2020). Greater involvement in online activities is expected, and the technological and institutional development of online activities during COVID-19 will contribute to an increase in online activities post-COVID-19 compared to the pre-COVID-19 period, with consequent impacts on mobility. Changes in urban mobility will not only depend on the degree of adoption of online activities, but also on other factors such as transport systems, adoption of shared mobility, advances in transport technologies, urban form, urban policies and regulations, and social factors (Lyons, Mokhtarian, Dijst and Böcker, 2018; Mouratidis et al., 2021; Shokouhyar, Shokoohyar, Sobhani and Gorizi, 2021).

Understanding the degree of change in the various online activities due to COVID-19 is a necessary step to obtain information on the present and future of virtual mobility and its implications not only for transport in cities but also to get a general picture of the new set-up of citizens' daily lives, who are increasingly inclined to adopt smart working solutions that go well with the green aspects for which there is an increase in the degree of awareness and a greater propensity on the part of citizens to adopt responsible and environmentally friendly behavior. Hopefully, very soon with the acceleration and success of the vaccine

campaign, the pandemic will be behind us. But it would be very serious not to capitalize on the virtuous circle between productivity and ecological sustainability.

6 FEASIBILITY STUDIES ON THE INTRODUCTION OF WORKING AT HOME: A GLOBAL OVERVIEW

Since the outbreak of COVID-19 in the world, technological progress has been used to enable companies and public administrations worldwide to continue working. This has come to fruition with the introduction of so-called “work at home” smart, better known in Italy as '*smart working*'. *Smart working* is CALLED “lavoro smart” by Law No. 82, 22 and regulated by the Legislative Decree of 17 March 2020 (in Italy). According to the Observatory on Smart Working of the Politecnico di Milano (Italy), *smart working* is a "managerial philosophy based on giving people back flexibility and autonomy in the choice of spaces, times and tools to be used, in exchange for greater accountability for results".

Smart work allows workers to work off the employer's premises; but this is only a corollary of a different conception of offices, their organization, and work supported by digital technologies. Recent socio-economic and technological changes in business environments have enabled new ways of working based on flexible working arrangements and extensive use of information technologies that support employees to work potentially at any time and space (De Leede and Heuver, 2016). Such approaches are generally referred to as '*smart working*' practices (Boorsma and Mitchell, 2011; Gastaldi et al., 2014; Zheltoukhova, 2014; McEwan, 2016). More comprehensively, smart working has been defined as an smart and dynamic way of working that leads to high performance, higher productivity and better job satisfaction resulting in a 'triple-win' configuration for customers, employees, and organizations (Gastaldi et al., 2014; Zheltoukhova, 2014; McEwan, 2016). In this regard, many scholars have pointed to a new paradigm shift that "is driven by extreme changes in approaches to work, work cultures, corporate architectures, premises, decision-making, communications and collaboration" (Boorsma and Mitchell, 2011).

Others, more cautiously, have referred to the evolutionary changes in work and management practices that are enabled by technological advances and that promote both organizational agility and new workforce expectations (e.g., Zheltoukhova, 2014; McEwan, 2016; Bednar and Welch, 2019). The application of work at home regime, requires cross-cutting interventions in organizational structure, workplace layout, work practices, and levels of human behavior. From a change management perspective, this involves the goal of building a collaborative ecosystem in which trust, flexibility, autonomy, and employee capabilities take primacy (Zheltoukhova, 2014; McEwan, 2016). Such an environment requires a profound cultural evolution, which can only take place when it is supported by a broader intervention in management capabilities. This global change has not developed uniformly but has differentiated by adapting to the different contexts in which it has taken root.

With the pandemic of COVID-19, the percentage of teleworkers has increased enormously.

ILO (International Labour Organisation) estimated that 7.9 per cent of the world's workforce (260 million workers) were already working from home permanently before the pandemic. Globally, among employees, 2.9% worked exclusively or mainly from home before the COVID-19 pandemic (ILO, 2020).

A 23 March survey of 250 large companies in Argentina found, for example, that 93% had adopted teleworking as a policy in response to the COVID-19 pandemic. But adapting to teleworking is not so simple. Although many companies recognize the benefits of teleworking, some have found it difficult to make the transition. In Japan, for example, a survey conducted by the Japan Association for Chief Financial Officers of

577 CFOs and CFOs (before the announcement of the state of emergency) found that while 96% of respondents agreed with the importance of teleworking, 31% of companies were unable to adopt teleworking because the paperwork was not yet digitized and the internal rules and procedures required for teleworking were not ready. Concerns about the confidentiality of information or possible security breaches also limited the adoption of teleworking. In addition, the economic downturn affected the demand for both home workers and industrial teleworkers, so even if workers could have done their work from home, they would not have been able to do so (von Broembsen, 2020).

Since the beginning of the pandemic, there has been a considerable volume of research on the potential of working from home as a response to the crisis.

Teleworking increased significantly during COVID-19, in various contexts including Asia, Europe and the United States (de Haas et al., 2020; Eurofound, 2020; Okubo, 2020; Shamshiripour et al., 2020).

Evaluating the economic impact of 'social distancing' measures taken to halt the spread of COVID-19 raises a fundamental question about the modern economy: how many jobs can be done at home? The most famous research was carried out by two scholars (Dingel and Neiman, 2020)² who used occupational descriptions from the Occupational Information Network (O*NET) to estimate the degree to which various occupations in the United States could be performed remotely. The researchers classified the feasibility of working at home for all occupations and combining this classification with occupational employment counts showed that 37% of American jobs "can plausibly be done from home". These jobs account for 46% of all US wages. Applying the occupational classification to 85 other countries reveals that low-income economies have a lower share of jobs that can be done at home.

Albrieu (2020), Foschiatti and Gasparini (2020), and Guntin (2020) applied Dingel and Neiman's methodology to Argentina and Uruguay, concluding that 26% to 29% of Argentineans and 20% to 34% of Uruguayan workers hold occupations that can be performed remotely, while Martins (2020) estimates that 30% of jobs can be performed from home in Portugal. Finally, Boeri et al. (2020), using a slightly adapted methodology, estimated the potential for working from home to be 24% for Italy, 28% for France, 29% for Germany, 25% for Spain, and 31% for Sweden and the UK.

Variations on Dingel and Neiman's methodology have dominated the literature, perhaps because they are based on a reasonably objective measure of whether or not each occupation can be done from home. The limitation of this methodology is that the O*NET data are for the United States and can, at best, be used for economies whose work environment is similar and cannot be replicated in developing countries. Nevertheless, Gottlieb et al. (2020) used the methodology of Dingel and Neiman, showing different estimates for agriculture in developing countries. Saltiel (2020) estimates the share of work that can be done from home in developing economies using surveys of occupations in low-income settings. Following the approach of Dingel and Neiman, Saltiel studies skills for employability and productivity to define the feasibility of working from home in as many as 23 countries. The advantage of using this data is that it addresses the concerns raised by defining the feasibility of working at home based on the economic context of the United States. Saltiel notes that few jobs can be done at home in developing countries (about 5%).

² https://bfi.uchicago.edu/wp-content/uploads/BFI_White-Paper_Dingel_Neiman_3.2020.pdf

These percentages reflect the behavioral, cultural, technological, and ethical habits of *smart working* practices in different countries that need to be taken into account to study the evolving dynamics of smart working approaches to promote and support the introduction of *smart working*.

7 THE EXPLOSION OF DIGITAL PLATFORMS

The introduction of digital infrastructures passes through the diffusion of a series of digital platforms that during the pandemic period had their peak of expansion, spreading widely in every aspect of our daily, personal and professional lives. There are several online tools and portals; among them, we find Zoom, Cisco Webex, Microsoft Teams, Google Meet, Skype, jitsi meet, facebook workplace, EzTalks and Big Blue Botton, and many others.

We went to analyze some of them and according to some studies³ it turned out that Zoom was the fastest-growing video conferencing app in 2016 and has not slowed down since. In the last three years, Zoom has seen an incredible 876% growth in the number of customers. By comparison, Cisco Webex in second place has grown 91% over the same period. As with Amazon, the pandemic crisis has simply accelerated Zoom's already robust growth. The reason for Zoom's explosion lies in its straightforward company policy of 'making video communication frictionless' This statement provides clarity to every member of the Zoom team that every action must never increase the customer's effort or increase its degree of complexity. Zoom has grown faster than its much larger competitors because it has made things easy for its users. Other companies have used a similar approach to take on the competition. Whatsapp has surpassed other messaging apps with an onboarding process, allowing new users to invite their friends with a tap of their screen. Amazon's Jeff Bezos spoke of 'frictionless shopping' in 1997, a time when many retailers were still trying to decide how important e-commerce was. History shows that smart start-ups that are relentless in creating an effortless customer experience can outperform much larger competitors. Zoom was founded by Eric Yuan, who left Cisco's Webex unit to focus on mobile-optimized video conferencing. Webex was the dominant videoconferencing player before Zoom surpassed them. Zoom's customer base to date stands at around 200 million users, up from 10 million in the pre-covid period⁴.

Another of the most widely used applications to cope with the social distancing caused by the pandemic is Microsoft's TEAMS. In mid-March 2020, the service became temporarily inaccessible following an unexpected spike in accesses; in fact, Teams went from 32 million daily active users to 44 million in just one week. The exponential growth is the result of the use of the service in Europe, a region where Teams was still relatively unpopular in the pre-pandemic period. This renewed success allowed Microsoft to provide an interesting general snapshot of working from home in the days of the coronavirus. The first obvious consequence is that Teams saw a spike in the use of communication features: it was seen that the time of use of the conferencing functions reached, adding all users together, 2.7 billion minutes in a single day.

This figure marks an unprecedented record for the app: we are talking about a 200% increase compared to the pre-pandemic figure (the pre-pandemic figure was 900 million minutes per day).

The video conferencing function, on the other hand, increased by 1000% in March 2020 alone. The companies that like video communication the most are those in Norway and the Netherlands with 60%, while the figure stops at 47% in the UK and 38% in the US.

³ 2020 Businesses @ Work (<https://www.okta.com/businesses-at-work/2020/>)

⁴ <https://www.forbes.com/sites/rogerdooley/2020/09/30/how-zoom-conquered-video-conferencing/?sh=2ada3be25a97>

Microsoft has created a timeline linking the use of its service to certain socially relevant events such as lockdowns. And Italy is the country where Microsoft has recorded the highest increase in usage. The unexpected spike in the use of Teams has had important implications for Microsoft, which is now implementing its platform. This is confirmed by China, where, despite the progressive relaxation of restrictive measures, Teams usage figures remain consistent with those recorded during the peak of the epidemic⁵⁶.

The pandemic has rewritten the rules in many areas and interfacing with colleagues via a webcam has now become the standard. The question is how long this new approach will last.

Those who started using these services have continued to do so. During the first quarter of 2021, installations of the main apps increased by 51% compared to the first quarter of 2020. This growth stood at 35% in the second quarter of this year. It remains to be seen how long this large-scale usage will last⁷.

8 THE FUTURE OF "WORK AT HOME" HABITS BETWEEN CORPORATE CONCERNS AND EMPLOYEE RIGHTS

The use of digital technologies is such an immersive and all-encompassing experience that it is easy to lose track of time while using them. In this regard, a study was conducted on the use of technology by more than 61,000 Microsoft employees, according to which the working week was extended by about 10 per cent⁸.

According to a new report, employees who worked at home during the COVID-19 lockout saw the length of their working days increase. The changing nature of work during the crisis was studied by the US National Bureau of Economic Research (NBER).

"It is unclear whether this increase in the average length of the working day is an advantage or a disadvantage for employee well-being," concludes the report by researchers from Harvard Business School and New York University.

On the one hand, the flexibility to choose own working hours to meet family needs can empower employees, giving them some freedom over their schedule. On the other hand, changing working hours can be a consequence of a blurred distinction between work and personal life, where it becomes easy to overwork due to the lack of a clear demarcation between the office and home.

The authors studied 3.1 million workers from more than 21,000 companies in more than a dozen cities in North America, Europe and the Middle East. They analyzed digital data on meetings and e-mails from eight weeks before the lockdown to eight weeks after. Analyzing the time between the first and last e-mail sent or meeting attended in 24 hours, they found that the average working day increased by 48.5 minutes, in part due to the increased number of e-mails sent after working hours. They also found that the total number of daily meetings per person increased by 12.9 per cent and the average number of participants increased by 13.5 per cent.

With millions of people taking part in this work-from-home experiment, it is worth asking the question: how do people and companies feel about working from home? Digital technologies have made it possible for many workers to do their work anytime, anywhere, with both advantages and disadvantages. A flexible

⁵ <http://indacodirect.it/microsoft-teams-non-si-tornera-indietro-lo-smartworking-sara-la-nuova-norma/>

⁶ <https://www.theverge.com/2020/4/9/21214314/microsoft-teams-usage-coronavirus-pandemic-work-habit-change>

⁷ <https://www.hdblog.it/mobile/articoli/n542081/zoom-meet-teams-video-conferenze-boom/>

⁸ <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2021/10/microsoft-study-covid19-work-hours/>

schedule, the possibility to work from anywhere and no more commuting were the main advantages reported. Of course, not everything is positive about working from home.

The main problem faced by remote workers was 'disconnection' from work. Without the clear change of location and defined office hours, many people found it more difficult to divide their personal and professional time. Eurofound data show that teleworkers are twice as likely to exceed the 48-hour working time limit, get insufficient rest, and work in their free time, with repercussions on their physical and mental health. To address this problem, there have been calls for a "right to disconnect". This report is based on case studies illustrating the implementation and impact of the right to disconnect in the workplace. It builds on previous Eurofound research showing an increase in collective agreements providing for the right to disconnect in countries that have enshrined this right in their legislation. With the exponential growth of teleworking brought about by the pandemic of COVID-19, it shows that:

- Workers from home are twice as likely to exceed the 48-hour working time limit as on-site workers and are significantly more likely to work in their free time. Following the shift to teleworking during the pandemic, this is likely to lead to more hybrid working arrangements in the future, highlighting whether existing labour legislation is fit for purpose.
- The experience of the first four member states to introduce rules and agreements on the right to disconnect before 2021 has shown the key role of social partners in ensuring that these rules are translated into reality on the ground. In countries with weaker industrial relations, legislation can provide a fallback option to ensure compliance with minimum standards.
- The introduction of the right to disconnect in companies has revealed that a 'soft' approach through awareness-raising, training and management of out-of-hours connection is more common than a 'hard disconnect', which interrupts access to company communication at specific times.
- New agreements and texts that address the right to disconnect will need to consider the issues that lead to the 'perceived' need for constant connection, such as workload, lack of training and work processes that fuel over-connection. High-level buy-in and regular reinforcement of the message on the importance of the right to disconnect will be critical to its success.
- Although there is a lack of evidence of the impact of the right to disconnect on employee health and well-being, work-life balance, gender equality and company performance, the experiences of social partners at the company level suggest that positive changes in the company culture are taking place following the introduction of the right to disconnect⁹¹⁰.

The disadvantages do not only affect employees; despite the popularity of remote working, not all companies have embraced the concept. Although there may be technical or security-related reasons behind resistance to remote working, a major obstacle is a simple resistance to change. More than 50% of companies that did not have a flexible or remote workplace policy cited long-standing company policy' as a reason. Managers are concerned that productivity and concentration will decrease if people work in more informal locations. Furthermore, if people do not work in the same physical location, managers believe that team cohesion and corporate culture might suffer. On the other hand, the cost savings associated with remote working can win over many companies. Research has found that a typical employer can save about \$11,000 per year for each person working remotely half the time. In addition, switching to virtual meetings in some cases can also be a significant cost saver. Location flexibility is not only a way to satisfy current employees. Companies that do

⁹ <https://www.eurofound.europa.eu/>

¹⁰ https://www.eurofound.europa.eu/sites/default/files/ef_publication/field_ef_document/ef21049en.pdf

not embrace flexible working may find themselves at a disadvantage when hiring new talent. Almost two-thirds of applicants say that choice of location is a key consideration when choosing an employer. Block measures highlighted the value of workplace flexibility, particularly for people with children. A total of 86% of parents now want to work flexibly, compared to 46% pre-coronavirus. As the economy slowly begins to reopen, it remains to be seen whether or not COVID-19 has accelerated the inevitable trends in workplace culture in the long run¹¹.

9 OTHER REALITIES LINKED TO THE ADVENT OF DIGITAL INFRASTRUCTURES: THE METAVERSE

The wide spread of digital infrastructures to make up for the lack of physical and social contact has brought another world into the limelight: the metaverse¹².

The metaverse is a vast expanse of digital space focused on social connection, in a synthetic hypothetical environment linked to the physical world. In the metaverse, users can interact with each other in real time and obtain similar and sometimes additional experiences to those they experience in the real world. The metaverse, however, should not be confused with virtual reality as we know it today. In fact, in the latter, users only interact with each other within a given environment, e.g. a video game, provided they have the same tool such as a 3D visor or other. These limitations therefore prevent interaction with users from other virtual environments or who do not have the same tool. The metaverse, on the contrary, is huge community cyberspace in which people - in the guise of 'avatars' - work, play, and develop interpersonal relationships by meeting according to the normal dynamics of everyday life.

The metaverse could therefore represent the natural evolution of the Internet. People experience and perceive, also thanks to the aid of specific devices (e.g. gloves or other garments capable of simulating what is perceived by the avatar and transferring it directly onto the human body), two parallel realities that intertwine and intermingle. This integration between the physical and real worlds is another of the main characteristics of meta-verses, namely their contiguity with the real space of which they represent the extension. Another feature of the metaverse is the overcoming of the constraints of time and space of the real world that, at the same time, regulate and limit human behavior.

Many of these cyberspaces currently exist or are being developed by organizations operating in different sectors: to name a few Diesel, Maison Margiela, Gucci, and Balenciaga in the luxury sector; Decentraland, Blocktopia, Sandbox and Star Atlas in that of online gaming; Facebook (now Meta) is turning its social network into a metaverse; Microsoft and Amazon will be the next to present their own interactive virtual spaces.

A key aspect of the metaverse is the interoperability between the various digital worlds, which is still in its infancy. The ultimate metaverse should be represented by a sum of interconnected spaces in which one can move freely from one to another, with people represented by the same avatar in all places, in which one can transport goods from one place to another, and in which one can use the same currency for purchases or different but interchangeable currencies.

The themes inherent to the metaverse have a strongly interdisciplinary application, involving aspects of computer science, social sciences (e.g. the sociology of networks), economics, and even complex legal issues

¹¹ <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2020/06/coronavirus-covid19-remote-working-office-employees-employers>

¹² "Metaverse" is a term coined by Neal Stephenson in the cyberpunk culture book "Snow Crash" (1992), described by the author as a kind of virtual reality shared via the Internet, where one is represented in three dimensions through one's avatar.

that take their cue, as usual, from the interpretation of an underlying reality that is constantly changing and therefore difficult to codify.

The metaverse has developed through three consequential steps:

1. The digital twins
2. The digital natives
3. The coexistence of physical and virtual reality - so-called surreality.

Digital twins reflect the properties of their physical counterparts and the connection between virtual and digital twins occurs through their data. The connection between the physical world and the metaverse through digital twins occurs through key enabling technologies, e.g. blockchain, and the inclusion of avatars in the new ecosystem, together with content creation, data interoperability, social acceptance, security, privacy and trustworthiness. The metaverse integrates a variety of new technologies: artificial intelligence, interactive technology, cloud and edge computing (prospectively, quantum computing), 5G and 6G, and the Internet of Things. Furthermore, the metaverse is based on decentralization based on technologies including distributed computing (distributed computing) and distributed storage (distributed storage), in tune with the blockchain architecture.

The main component of the metaverse is the so-called 'Extended Reality', i.e. the set of three technologies or, rather, three tools for interactive and immersive experience: Virtual Reality, Augmented Reality, and Mixed Reality. Virtual Reality replaces the vision of the physical world with a digitally produced scene that can represent a duplicate of the real world or places in an imaginary universe. Immersion in the virtual dimension occurs through the use of software installed on PCs or smartphones together with wearable devices such as visors, headsets, gloves, and cyber suits.

Augmented Reality, on the other hand, makes it possible to add or subtract elements to the real-world vision - for example, the possibility of placing a piece of furniture chosen from a digital catalog on the image of a real space. Mixed Reality, finally, combines Virtual and Augmented Reality, allowing the fusion of the real and virtual worlds, creating new environments in which people, physical and digital objects coexist and interact in real time.

The metaverse is a world already present in many areas listed in the followings:

Healthcare

Mixed reality tools are already being used by the healthcare sector⁸. Devices such as HoloLens⁹ are used in training, pre-procedure planning, and cardiac interventions. In addition to pre-operative CT images, MRI, and 3D scans, Mixed Reality tools are used to visualize crucial patient data in real time such as heart rate, body temperature, blood pressure, and respiratory rate.

Defense

The military sector has been experimenting with Virtual and Augmented Reality tools for some time now. Tactical Augmented Reality (TAR), for instance, is a technology that has added functionality to night vision goggles (NVG) by showing the precise position of a soldier, allies and hostile forces. Being directly attached to the helmet, it avoids distractions caused by the need to check the handheld GPS. Another military

application is the Synthetic Training Environment designed to provide soldiers with a more realistic training experience by placing them in more physically and psychologically demanding combat scenarios.

Manufacturing Industry

In addition to process and product training, metaverse technologies can reduce the number of workplace accidents as personnel can learn safety precautions by participating in simulations of risky circumstances. A further application of such technologies in the manufacturing sector is the design of factory layouts by being able to choose the most efficient location of equipment. The application of such technologies is predominant in the design. For example, Ford's designers use Gravity Sketch, which allows 3D models to be created using gestures, resulting in virtual vehicles that can be rotated and viewed from any angle. According to Ford management, the use of such technology reduces design time from weeks to hours. Immersive tools are also incorporated into products to enhance the customer experience, as in the case of Nissan, which uses augmented reality in some vehicles to show the driver the situation of the road around a corner and behind buildings.

Education

These technologies in perspective will enable students to learn faster by immersing themselves in a virtual reality rather than through mere reading. For the current generation, accustomed to images rather than written text, the use of such technology may be more motivating.

Electronic commerce

Virtual metaverse spaces are the ideal place for commerce both for consumers who can check the quality and fit of a product before purchase and for retailers who can offer product customisation, expand their customer base and, consequently, revenues. In this case, the shopping experience is mixed, online for product selection and offline for delivery to the customer. In the metaverse, however, there are also the digital representations of the customers, their avatars, which in turn constitute a market as in the case of Coca Cola, which made \$575,000 in revenue by selling sports jackets with logos for avatars to wear in the Digiland metaverse¹⁰. Many other brands are present in the metaverse.

Diesel, Maison Margiela, Gucci and Balenciaga in the luxury sector; Decentraland, Blocktopia, Sandbox and Star Atlas in the online gaming sector; Microsoft and Amazon will be the next to present their own interactive virtual spaces.

Social networks

With the metaverse, traditional content-oriented social networks will be transformed into interactive and immersive three-dimensional virtual social worlds. Facebook (now renamed Meta) announced the transformation of its social network into a metaverse, with an investment of ten billion dollars over five years.

Entertainment

Disney is planning the evolution of its theme parks by rebuilding them in its metaverse.

Meta-verses are spaces where one can not only admire places, monuments, and works of art but also do business.

On Decentraland, for instance, it is possible to buy land to build on, rent out, and so on. To be precise, you can buy NFT (LAND) representing the ownership of land by paying for it in MANA, the cryptocurrency used

in Decentraland. To give an idea of the value of transactions in this metaverse, in November 2021, a plot of 1,856 square meters was sold for 2.43 million MANA equivalent to USD 913,000.

Decentraland's economy has grown so large that major brands have started to advertise and market their products on the platform. Coca Cola turned over USD 575,000 with the sale of sports jackets with logos for avatars to wear in Digiland.

Metaverses represent worlds in which trade is becoming increasingly important along with the market value of the companies that produce the technology to support it. According to a Bloomberg Intelligence report, the market value of companies operating in the metaverse is expected to reach \$800 billion by the middle of this decade and \$2.5 trillion by 2030¹³.

Within the metaverse, however, trade takes place on two levels. On the one hand, as we have seen, there is the presence of shops that, in essence, act as storefronts and traditional e-commerce, while allowing for a more immersive experience in which the customer chooses a product that exists in the real world and pays for it with fiat currency. In parallel, in the metaverse, there are properties, goods and other values that are represented by NFTs or, more precisely, are NFTs whose exchanges take place through digital currencies. The metaverse, through the interactions between avatars, makes possible value co-creation strategies in which individual virtual nodes actively participate in such creation, receiving remuneration in tokens/cryptocurrencies that is usually lacking in many traditional business models. Even feedback on the Internet (such as, for instance, reviews on Tripadvisor) does not entail any direct remuneration for the user, who for his part provides valuable big data that feeds increasingly advanced profiled marketing strategies. With the metaverse, there is a customer-centric quality leap, which places the user at the center of the co-creation and sharing of new value. The metaverse's currency is currently represented by controversial cryptocurrencies, linked to blockchain technologies.

Pioneering investments in the metaverse are based on prospects of medium- to long-term economic returns, which in turn depend on the revenue model embedded in business models and disruptive strategies, which are highly innovative in scope and marked by discontinuity. These investments are made first and foremost by Big Tech (starting with the Faangs - Facebook, Amazon, Apple, Netflix and Google), intent on creating new lifestyles and entertainment, in the hope that they will become market standards, guaranteeing the promoters the role of first mover and standard settler, from which oligopolistic rents may derive (if barriers to entry for new competitors are created)¹⁴.

9.1 BLOCKCHAIN TECHNOLOGIES

We are in a historical moment in which innovation is catalyzing a great deal of attention, but all too often we remain stuck in a still fairly generalized confusion, between Cryptocurrencies, Bitcoin, Blockchain Platforms, Smart Contracts, and so on. Blockchain, which means blockchain,¹ exploits the characteristics of a computer network of nodes and allows a register containing data and information (transactions) to be managed and updated in an open, shared, and distributed manner without the need for central control and verification entity.

This innovation potentially does away with banks, notaries, financial institutions, and so on. Blockchain technologies are included in the broader family of Distributed Ledger technologies, i.e. systems that rely on

¹³ BLOOMBERG, Investing in the 'Metaverse', 2021 <http://www.bloomberg.com>

¹⁴https://www.researchgate.net/publication/358667569_II_metaverso_tra_realta_digitale_e_aumentata_innovazione_tecnologica_e_catena_del_valore/link/620e56bfeb735c508adb1866/download

a distributed ledger, which can be read and modified by multiple nodes in a network. To validate the changes to be made to the ledger, in the absence of a central entity, the nodes must reach a consensus. How consensus is reached and the structure of the ledger are some of the features that characterize the different Distributed Ledger technologies.

Blockchain is thus a subfamily of technologies, or as it is often referred to, a set of technologies, in which the ledger is structured as a blockchain containing transactions, and consensus is distributed across all nodes in the network. All nodes can participate in the validation process of transactions to be included in the register.

The relationship between Blockchain and Bitcoin is as close as it is crucial. Released in 2009, Bitcoin was the first cryptocurrency to use a new type of distributed ledger, known as the Blockchain. Among the innovations introduced by Bitcoin was the fact that each transaction was legitimized by a decentralized network and not by central authorities. Many platforms could contribute to enabling the Internet of Value: from Bitcoin to Ethereum, from Iota to Nano, and from Zcash to Monero. There are now over 1,000 platforms and new ones are born every day. Each is characterized by different configurations, however, it is possible to identify 7 common characteristics of blockchain technology:

- Digitilization
- decentralization
- traceability of transfers
- disintermediation
- transparency and verifiability
- immutability of the register
- programmability of transfers

The Internet of Value is a system that makes it possible to exchange value over the Internet as easily as information is exchanged today. It is defined as a digital network of nodes that transfer value to each other through a system of algorithms and cryptographic rules that allows consensus to be reached, even in the absence of trust, on changes to a distributed ledger that keeps track of unique digital asset transfers. Within this Universe, therefore, orbit different galaxies, or rather different platforms that enable the development of Blockchain solutions. These platforms can be categorized into two large groups: permissionless and permissioned.

Permissionless blockchains are those in which anyone can participate in the transaction validation process and anyone can become a node in the network. Among the most famous permissionless ones are Bitcoin and Ethereum, but many others have generated their cryptographic currencies. Not only bitcoin we are talking about decentralized digital currencies that use cryptographic techniques to guarantee the security of exchanges between users. With so many differences from traditional currencies, many new platforms have gained the limelight. We are talking about Ethereum, Ripple, RopE, Hyperledger, and many others (over 900).

Blockchains are characterized by restricted network access to a few authorized participants and a validation process delegated to a small group of actors. These include Corda and Hyperledger¹⁵.

¹⁵ https://blog.osservatori.net/it_it/blockchain-spiegazione-significato-applicazioni

9.2 THE METAVERSE'S MOST POPULAR PLATFORMS

Many digital worlds are emerging that cater to consumers and can be accessed via browsers, apps, or virtual reality devices. Here are the main platforms for entering the metaverse

- Decentraland is a virtual reality world of the metaverse created by Ethereum. In this virtual universe, users, once registered, can create virtual buildings, houses, and parks and charge others for their visits. All virtual items in Decentraland can be purchased with a cryptocurrency called MANA. Decentraland also hosted a music festival with Paris Hilton. Entering the Decentraland metaverse is easy, just go to the site create an account with your avatar and start exploring. Luxury brands such as Gucci, Dolce & Gabbana, LV, Etro, fast fashion chains such as Zara, H&M, Benetton, and sportswear, in full FOMO (Fear of missing out) effect, have not missed the opportunity to open their flagship stores in the Metaverse Fashion District, creating real immersive experiences for users. One example of this was the METAVERSE FASHION WEEK, which took place last March in Decentraland and was the world's first and largest fully digital fashion week with four days of fashion shows and more than 60 well-known brands, designers, and artists¹⁶.
- Sandbox is a virtual metaverse that has become popular since announcing its partnership with Meta. Its avatars have a blocky visual style like Minecraft and can build, own, and monetize using NFT and SAND. Sandbox has also partnered with over 165 brands to create avatars in the virtual world of celebrities such as Snoop Dog and The Walking Dead. The Sandbox platform is not yet available but while waiting you can visit the site and interact with the community.
- Stageverse is a new virtual platform for immersive experiences. It debuted at the Muse concert and allows users to watch concerts through 360° 3D footage and special effects. Stageverse can be accessed through the Oculus app¹⁷.

10. GUIDELINES FOR AN INCREASINGLY DIGITAL FUTURE

Different opinions are shared about the *smart working* scenario, once the emergency is over. On the one hand, people believe that the status quo will be restored (*smart working* one or two days a week, in large companies); on the other hand, they propose that everyone will continue to work remotely. Probably what will happen is that a new balance will be established between on-site and remote work, a 'ubiquitous' quality of work that can be done anywhere.

The applications of ubiquitous work are an opportunity to finally and profoundly change organisations' work, and to improve efficiency and quality of life: it is up to the management of organizations to initiate and lead the necessary profound processes of change, with the appropriate professional support; up to the institutions to set up the material, financial and training infrastructure to facilitate these developments.

The main challenge will be to adequately extend smart working to SMEs, smaller Public Administration organizations, and third sector organizations, realities which, before the lockdown, had a percentage of *smart working* applications even for just one day a week less than 15% and 16% respectively. For this to happen, it will first of all be necessary to support those who intend to undertake such a path of change, taking into account above all the differences between these companies and Public Administrations.

Two types of actions could be envisaged:

- **policy and transversal actions;**

¹⁶ <https://www.punto-informatico.it/criptoaluta-decentraland-mana-coin/>

¹⁷ <https://www.digital4.biz/executive/metaverso-cos-e-possibili-applicazioni/>

- **clinical and development actions of individual organizations.**

Actions on policies and transversal actions

- It is necessary to integrate and promote multidisciplinary research on the *smart working* experiment to understand what happened. The activity should be the result of synergic action by research public bodies (e.g. CNR in Italy), universities, large companies, and trade unions.
- *Smart working* (or ubiquitous work) requires public funding programs for training initiatives, and work organization change sites both within companies and in the Public Administration.
- A new regulatory framework must be developed.
- Strong investments must be made in telematic networks (also based on the resources expected from the European Union).
- Consider tax incentives to reorganize offices, home environments, and the configuration of cities.
- Support the realities (both entrepreneurial and public) that are slower on this path.
- Professional support available for SMEs and the public administration offered by universities, IT and consulting companies, etc., enabling training activities for these realities with sustainable methods and costs.

Clinical and development actions of individual organizations

We start from the assumption that *smart working* is a systemic change in the organization. This is why it must be planned and managed in the best possible way in each organization, differentiated by the type of process and people. Developing *smart working* in a company, a public administration or an association requires the following aspects to be taken into account:

- *Smart working* concept: it is necessary to agree on the definition of *smart working* for management, workers, and the trade union. Is it just remote working, i.e. a new managerial philosophy, or a new way of running the business, or something else?.
- Legal aspects: many legal aspects must be taken into account (e.g., data security, protection of employee privacy, employer responsibility for possible accidents, and more).
- Infrastructure: today, digital connection networks are unequally available in different areas of the single Country and in different Countries. Developments must be planned realistically considering the availability of infrastructure.
- Ways of managing work-life balance: in recent months, an experiment in recombining work-at-home and personal life took place involving over 8 million people. Some were happy about it, while others reported serious problems of overload, interference between life and work, and stress. Women with children and those living in small houses were penalized. A new way of working that reconciles life and work in the same place must be encouraged, regulated, and negotiated with individuals, if not conceived, designed in individual contexts by activating training paths for managers, middle managers, and worker participation.
- Mindset: *smart working* requires a different mindset and ability to reconcile work and personal life for workers and leaders. *Smart working* needs preparation, training.
- Proportion between on-site and remote work: once the emergency is over, it will be necessary to re-proportion these spheres, inevitably involving imposing structural economic dimensions. All these aspects have to be taken into account: use of company space, use of coworking areas, valorization of peripheral areas or hamlets as distributed work locations, reconfiguration of transport, management of catering and hotel

services around company sites, and much more. This is a matter for public policy, but there is a strong role for companies that relocate work between their company and other locations.

- Office interior design: spacing requirements give rise to new ideas of how to organize office layouts, beyond single offices and open spaces.

- Redesigning home spaces: many workers need advice and resources to redesign their home spaces. But above all, smart working requires and enables the reconfiguration that has been expected for half a century of organization and work.

- Organisation and socio-technical system: the professional office made up of experts and professionals has long been accustomed to working remotely, as well as the management office where guidance and direction can also be provided remotely.

- 'Factory offices': this working approach is not suited to work by objectives and competencies, and employes the vast majority of people. There is now an important opportunity to reduce the weight of factory offices and move towards self-regulated organizational structures and professionalization of people. We need to develop organizational forms that differ from those conceived so far, based on the idea that the office is only a portion of an organizational chart where tasks and duties are managed. We need forms of microstructures or socio-technical systems that are 'small companies' that manage processes and measure results and are equipped with mechanisms for continuous adaptation to the external environment. This requires a reconfiguration of processes, cooperation technologies, the design of microstructures, management control systems, and visual management. Digital technologies are a powerful tool for building self-regulating teams. Without such changes, it will be very difficult to conceive of work based on achieving results and objectives.

- Work and professional system: the current ways of carrying out work, especially in factory offices, which are today based on tasks, duties, levels, and benefits reinforced by labor law and industrial relations, must be changed. Instead, a conception of work should be developed, based on open roles characterized by results, control over processes, self-regulated forms of cooperation, mastery of technology, domain skills, and social skills. In many cases, work should evolve towards broad-based trades and professions with an extended potential for flexibility and adaptation to changing roles and contexts.

- Industrial relations: industrial relations will have to strengthen their local (company, territorial, sectoral) dimensions and will have to become 'proactive'. Trade unions or representations will have to actively participate in change processes and not deal with them when they are already underway. To act in these areas, project paths must be activated to change the structures of organization, work, and relations.

We are therefore facing with an extraordinary opportunity to redesign work and organization for the future. The Fordist revolution was an opportunity to redesign not only machinery, but also industrial relations: nowadays the relationship between life, work, and incomes, is changing and is significantly impacting the way we work and the way we provide services to customers. The pandemic, in addition to its disastrous effects, has created a window of opportunity for innovators, an opportunity to be grasped: while large companies and administrations have demonstrated their ability to do so, it is necessary to support those realities that have encountered and are encountering greater difficulties to ensure that these changes become a widespread culture.

The new offices of the future (including part of the production plants) will have the following main connotations that emerge from existing best practices to become design paradigms.

The first connotation of the offices/industrial plants of the future is that they will be (more than today) socio-technical systems, which have their identity not in the places, nor even in the location in organization charts, but in being structures where organization, technology, small companies are combined to realize information processes, data valorization, research, decision-making systems, maintenance, innovation to obtain results. No more directorates, departments, sections, and representation of the organization as a hierarchy. They will be real organizational structures made by people working together in an organized manner, physically or through a screen.

These systems operate based on a different model from the Taylor-Fordist and bureaucratic one: the 4C model based on the sharing of objectives, values (work, innovation, inclusion), knowledge of the forms of their operationalization, monitoring, and choices of allocation of available resources:

- The forms of Cooperation among members, largely self-regulated;
- The extensive sharing of knowledge within and outside the region;
- Extensive Communication;
- The development of a cohesive and performing Community.

In a word, a socio-technical system that converges the organized work of many people and digital technologies towards results: these systems operate both within the walls of the same office and between people working in different places alone, but together. The amount of processes that can be conducted remotely depends on the ability to configure and manage processes and to maintain a vital, cohesive, and generative social system.

Every process that takes place in an office pursues and achieves different and integrated results: service, quality, quantity, cost, flexibility, and innovativeness, but also the quality of life for users and quality of working life.

The second connotation of the office/workplace of the future is that of an organization to achieve multiple and often very complex ends, which concern, at the same time, cost, competitiveness, and diversification strategies and strategies of physical and social compatibility. Structures, technologies, furnishings, rules, placement of people in places, and digital platforms must, therefore "speak" of the focus, of the strategy to be pursued, so that one operates for objectives and not for prescriptions and programs.

The third feature of the new offices/workplaces is the coexistence of concentric boundaries:

- local boundaries (which include teams, task forces, and specific organizational units, i.e. those socio-technical systems mentioned in the previous point and composed of people, technologies, processes, and results that take place either within physically identified locations or without a physical location);
- 'cosmopolitan' boundaries (involving borderless flows and networks linking people and socio-technical systems). At the center of these concentric circles is the person.

An office is conceived as a set of concentric places with the person and his or her profession at the center.

Every work activity simultaneously enters into a plurality of parallel universes: into a physical universe; into an operational universe; into a procedural universe; into decision-making and the creative universe; into a communicative universe. Within each of these 'universes' the different dimensions of the integrity of a person's working life are at play. People do not have to be together in one place to recognize, defend and design the quality of their working life as it was in the Fordist factory. People must recognize 'universes'. That

is, the processes in which they are placed, agree, negotiate, and work design to have results while protecting the quality of people's working lives. Digital platforms and their social rules become the virtual 'new factory' that must be designed and improved with participatory processes.

The fourth feature of the office of the future is therefore the co-presence of different dimensions of the real and the virtual in the same work process, all of which must be controlled to protect the quality of working life. This last one thus becomes a key criterion of job design and development, of job design and job crafting, in both its physical and virtual dimensions.

These criteria apply to a world of work that leaves behind the paradigms of hierarchical coordination and control that have generated so many devices whose inapplicability in teleworking worries many managers¹⁸.

11. CONCLUSIONS

There is no doubt that ICT and digital technology are entering and influencing strategies and industrial plans of companies of all sizes, worldwide. Industry 4.0, new customer experience, and smart workplace models are increasingly shared and implemented strategies, even in Italy.

On the other hand, for these models to spread and have concrete results for companies, it is necessary to rethink and review the underlying technological architectures and infrastructures.

Integration, openness, flexibility, agility, and speed are the keywords that digital transformation projects today demand from IT and its systems.

While the COVID-19 crisis has posed a huge challenge to many infrastructure systems - with direct consequences on social infrastructures such as health and education - the crisis has shown that a reliable infrastructure system, coupled with investments in innovative infrastructures, is the basis for global economic recovery.

The share of remote work will increase without eliminating work at presence. This will inevitably pose problems, as any self-respecting change does, but it will also generate a drive to responsibly and consciously balance people working time and private lifetime.

As far as the Italian panorama is concerned, the reorganization of the smart working system in the PA has already been expressly regulated^{19,20}. This law is the expression of a widespread feeling that cannot fail to consider smart working as a reality now rooted in the soul of the population.

We do not yet know what specifically the agreements will be, but we can make some predictions. Many other aspects will be defined between trade unions and employees; however, *smart working* will not disappear, and will be regulated and disciplined according to new criteria and guidelines. The future will therefore be dictated by so-called ubiquitous work.

At the corporate level, we also find a positive and proactive attitude regarding the integration of technological infrastructures and the adoption of *smart working*. Through this research project, it has

¹⁸ <https://www.hbritalia.it/speciale-gestire-le-crisi/2020/09/30/news/dallo-smart-working-al-lavoro-ubiquo-di-qualita-unopportunita-per-cambiare-il-lavoro-e-le-organizzazioni-1-14869/>

¹⁹ <https://www.altalex.com/documents/news/2021/09/17/green-pass-obbligatorio-lavoratori-pubblici-e-privati>

²⁰ Smart working will be the subject of a contractualisation between the Agency for the Negotiation Representation of Public Administrations (ARAN) and the civil service unions, and pending the agreement, discretion is granted to administrations to identify appropriate ways to apply smart working where it is unavoidable

emerged that, for medium and large companies, *smart working* is essentially the future of the working world: *smart working* is a great resource for better work management. This approach gives us an idea of how *smart working* has been perceived, as an opportunity for change.

The change in working methods is reflected in particular in the flexible organization of work, and in the balancing of work and private life: these are the two elements considered most important for the population, even before the reduction of company and employee costs, underlining a substantial improvement in general living conditions and the well-being of the whole worker societies.

This feeling is supported by the fact that productivity did not deteriorate; on the contrary, in most cases, it remained the same or even increased significantly.

Employees did not stop communicating with superiors or colleagues and meetings: they registered an increase of 42.5%. This use of video conferencing together with instant messaging leads to a widespread perception of hyper-connectedness with widespread fear of a possible loss of sociability and isolation.

At the corporate level, however, there is a general satisfaction, despite its sudden and unplanned adoption, so that several companies have already decided to (partially) maintain *smart working*.

This is a key factor that will greatly affect future selections of new personnel, as the inclusion of the total or hybrid Smart Working mode is very relevant, if not fundamental, to be able to find the figures sought by companies.

It is clear that companies are willing to invest in this new working modality, as they already invested in technology by providing employees with the appropriate tools such as smartphones and notebooks, but above all in courses and activities to redesign the company organization. To put *smart working* into practice, it is essential to work on the development of infrastructure and digital platforms. However, to achieve concrete results, it is essential to invest in the development of a culture of responsibility and autonomy and evolved organizational systems based on goal setting, communication, and continuous improvement. In short, the goal of *smart working* on a large scale implies managing a process of change that generates new values and new skills. In this framework, the coronavirus has been an important accelerator. However, the impact of the pandemic is not enough to achieve tangible and continuous results over time. This is why companies and workers must not be left to their own devices, but accompanied towards new goals, values, and behavioral patterns. In other words, the process of change toward smart working must be monitored, guided, and directed through a pluralistic and participatory process. All this must and can be the subject of joint planning between company and trade union, between employer and employee, leaving room for experimentation, remembering that digital infrastructures, *smart working*, the various digital infrastructures, and the innumerable worlds of the metaverse are explicative of a new social expression that seeks its connections in virtuality that has arrived in today's reality to build the new sociality of tomorrow.

However, the process is still in progress, considering that the need for continuous innovation requires speed and urgency, while changes in attitudes and behavior take time to mature. At first glance, this might seem a paradox; however, it simply entails breaking down the barriers that bind us to the formal organization and which we must strive to shape according to a new work organization in a process of continuous adaptation.

The legacy that Covid-19 leaves us is the knowledge that we live and will continue to live, in a history of maximum unpredictability. The ability to innovate and the adoption of new operating models that combine

digital and physical, solutions that mix strategy and flexibility, of new technical and human skills, are not the pillars of tomorrow's enterprise, but the requirements of today's enterprise.

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